

STUDY PROTOCOL

Prevalence and Patterns of Dietary Supplement Use Among Elite Athletes: A Systematic Review

Introduction / Background

Rationale and Objectives

Dietary supplement use is widespread in elite sport, yet reported prevalence, commonly used supplements, motivations for use, and sources of information vary considerably across sports and regions. Understanding the patterns of supplement use among elite athletes is critical for sports nutrition guidance, anti-doping education, and athlete health and safety, yet reported prevalence varies widely. Existing studies are fragmented and often context specific, limiting generalisability.

To our knowledge, no systematic review has exclusively focused on prevalence and patterns of supplement use specifically among elite athletes, a population with unique characteristics, pressures, and anti-doping considerations that warrant separate examination. This review will systematically synthesize available evidence to provide comprehensive and up-to-date estimates of prevalence of supplement use among elite athletes, identify commonly used products, and clarify reasons and influences for use. The findings will inform athletes, coaches, clinicians, and policy makers and support evidence-based guidance and education in elite sport.

Method

Eligibility criteria

Articles will be selected for the review if they are (1) written in English, (2) involve elite athletes, and (3) provide a quantitative assessment of the proportion of athletes using dietary supplements of any type, as defined by the DSHEA of 1994 (Dietary Supplement Health and Education Act of 1994). Titles will be first examined and then abstracts if the articles appear to involve athletes and either nutrition or dietary supplements. The full text of the article will be retrieved if there is a possibility that dietary supplements were included within the investigation.

For this review, elite athletes are defined as individuals who compete at national or international levels, participate in major competitive leagues or championships, or are members of recognized high-performance or professional sports programs.

Recreational, youth, university, and masters' athletes will be excluded unless results for elite athletes were reported separately. Studies that do not clearly define level of competition or are based solely on doping-control test samples will be excluded.

Primary outcome

- Prevalence of dietary supplement use among elite athletes

Secondary outcomes

- Frequently used dietary supplements.
- Motivations for dietary supplement use.
- Sources of information or recommendations for supplement use.

Search Strategy

This review will follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. Systematic literature searches were conducted in PubMed and Scopus. No limitations were placed on the dates of the searches, and the final search was completed in November 2025. After reviewing PubMed medical subject headings for 'dietary supplements' and 'elite athletes', keywords selected for the search included elite athlete, professional athlete, Olympic athlete, elite sport and professional sport. These keywords were combined with dietary supplement, nutrition supplement, nutritional supplement, supplement, ergogenic aid, sports supplement, prevalence, frequency, usage, use. The review protocol is registered in PROSPERO prior to data extraction, following pilot testing of the screening process to assess feasibility.

PubMed

("elite athlete*" OR "professional athlete*" OR "high performance athlete*" OR "competitive athlete*" OR "national athlete*" OR "international athlete*" OR "Olympic athlete*" OR "professional sport*" OR "elite sport*") AND ("dietary supplement*" OR "nutrition supplement*" OR "nutritional supplement*" OR supplement* OR "ergogenic aid*" OR "sports supplement*") AND (prevalence OR "frequency" OR "usage" OR "use")

Scopus

TITLE-ABS ("elite athlete*" OR "professional athlete*" OR "high performance athlete*" OR "competitive athlete*" OR "national athlete*" OR "international athlete*" OR "Olympic athlete*" OR "professional sport*" OR "elite sport*") AND ("dietary supplement*" OR "nutrition supplement*" OR "nutritional supplement*" OR supplement* OR "ergogenic aid*" OR "sports supplement*") AND (prevalence OR "frequency" OR "usage" OR "use") AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")

Data extraction

Data will be extracted using a standardized and piloted data extraction form developed for this review (Appendix A). The form will capture study characteristics, participant and sport-related information, methods of exposure assessment, prevalence estimates, types of dietary supplements used, motivations for use, sources of information or recommendations, and additional relevant notes. Data extraction will be performed independently by two researchers and discrepancies resolved by discussion and consultation with a third researcher.

Risk of bias assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal Checklist for Studies Reporting Prevalence Data (Appendix B). The checklist evaluates methodological quality across domains including sampling, measurement reliability, and appropriateness of statistical analysis.

Certainty Assessment

The quality of the evidence for all outcomes will be assessed using the GRADE approach, adapted for prevalence studies as high, moderate, low, or very low certainty. The rationale for each rating will be documented in the review.

Strategy for data synthesis

Data will be combined using quantitative synthesis methods, including meta-analysis of prevalence estimates where studies are sufficiently homogeneous. Pooled prevalence will be

calculated using random-effects models, with appropriate transformation of proportions where required. Where meta-analysis is not feasible, results will be summarized narratively and using descriptive statistics.

Appendix B: JBI Critical appraisal tool of the study

	Yes	No	Unclear	Not applicable
Q1. Was the sample frame appropriate to address the target population?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q2. Were study participants sampled in an appropriate way?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q3. Was the sample size adequate?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q4. Were the study subjects and the setting described in detail?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q5. Was the data analysis conducted with sufficient coverage of the identified sample?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q6. Were valid methods used for the identification of the condition?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q7. Was the condition measured in a standard, reliable way for all participants?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q8. Was there appropriate statistical analysis?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q9. Was the response rate adequate, and if not, was the low response rate managed appropriately?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>